

Revista Letras Raras, Scholarly Journal of Linguistics and Literature, v. 12, n. 3. 2023.

Languages and Literatures in contemporaneity

In the days leading up to the coming year, we announce the publication of the third regular edition of 2023, concluding the eleventh year of existence of "**Revista Letras Raras**" (RLR). As we prepare for the year-end celebrations, we take a moment to catch our breath after the dedicated work throughout this year, especially concerning the migration of all the issues published by this journal from 2012 to the present moment, from the old to the new Open Journal System (OJS) 3+ platform. This herculean task was made possible thanks to the competence and commitment of the entire RLR team. We have also inaugurated the dual assignment of Digital Object Identifier (DOI) to bilingual paper versions; thanks to Zenodo, an open repository developed by the European Open Science Infrastructure program (OpenAIRE).

Beyond the support of digital languages, this edition features an issue titled **Languages and Literatures in contemporaneity**, organised by Professors Alain-Philippe Durand from the University of Arizona (USA), Josilene Pinheiro-Mariz from the Federal University of Campina Grande (BRA), and Maria Rennally Soares da Silva from the Federal University of Paraíba (BRA). The thirteen papers comprising this issue cover areas such as *Language Dialogism*, *Sociodiscursive Interactionism*, *Discourse Analysis*, *Beliefs*, *Applied Linguistics*, *Didactics*, *Media Genres*, *Indigenous Literature*, *Comparative Literature*, *Literary Adaptation for Cinema and Literary Reception*. The edition also includes a literary translation of a text originally published in English, along with four texts of artistic creation.

This edition benefits from the collaboration of professors, students, and other scholars who are authors of papers, translations, and artistic or literary texts. They come from diverse institutions such as the University of Coimbra, Federal University of Northern Tocantins (UFNT), Federal University of Paraíba (UFPB), Federal University of Rio Grande (FURG), Federal Fluminense Institute of Education, Science, and Technology (IFFluminense), Federal University of Mato Grosso do Sul (UFMS), Federal Center for Technological Education of Minas Gerais (CEFET-MG), Federal University of Campina Grande (UFCG), State University of Paraíba (UEPB), State University of Rio

Grande do Norte (UERN), Federal University of Rio Grande do Norte (UFRN), Pontifical Catholic University of Minas Gerais (PUC Minas), Federal Rural University of Rio de Janeiro (UFRRJ), State University of Mato Grosso (UNEMAT), State University of Ceará (UECE), Municipal Network of Campos dos Goytacazes (SMECE/PMCG), and Duque de Caxias (SMEDC/PMDC).

The first of the thirteen papers, titled **Transdisciplinarity and dialogism as foundations of the teaching action: a proposal for a reading class**, by André de Souza from the Federal University of Northern Tocantins (UFNT), addresses the need to advance in constructing education based on universality through a socio-ideological debate. It has the aim of reflecting on how theoretical contributions, especially those related to transdisciplinarity, complexity theory, and Bakhtin's dialogical theory of language, can support the pedagogical practice of Portuguese language teachers. The paper suggests that these reflections can help these teachers face the challenges of education in the 21st century and broaden the socio-ideological awareness of educators.

The second paper, **Meetings with the teaching work: dimensions of the professional development in the pedagogical residence program/UFPB**, by Barthyra Cabral Vieira de Andrade from the Federal University of Paraíba (UFPB), highlights the importance of the training context in the pedagogical residence programme at the university. The authors aim to understand the process of constructing the teaching identity and professional development of literature students who are graduating as teachers. The analytical reflection is based on reading reflective reports produced between 2018 and 2019, emphasising different dimensions of this process. The paper highlights the development of residents as teachers, emphasising the collective dimension and the social and subjective aspects involved in this process.

The third paper, **Who can be a university student? A discursive analysis of the imaginary representation of public and private school students**, by Ariadne Siqueira de Medeiros and Rosely Diniz da Silva Machado from the Federal University of Rio Grande do Norte (UFRN), addresses the stigmatisation of public education as precarious and insufficient, in contrast to a misguided view of the quality of private education in Brazil. Using the perspective of Pecheux's Discourse Analysis, the study examines speeches of students from public and private schools in two apparently similar reports but differing in their conception of the entrance exam. The paper reveals how discourses about public and private schools align with the knowledge of the ruling class and serve the interests of the capitalist system.

In the sequence, the fourth paper is **Lusophone pluricentrality: what do IFFluminense languages licenciateship students know about portuguese in East Timor?**, by Leiliane Rezende da Silva Silveira, Raul Chatel Neto, and Thiago Soares de Oliveira from the Federal Fluminense Institute of Education, Science, and Technology (IFFluminense). It focuses on investigating the knowledge of students in the Language and Literature (Portuguese) programme at the institution regarding the historical relationship between Portuguese and East Timor. The methodology includes an initial bibliographic research, compiling theoretical data through the note-taking technique, followed by field research with the application of questionnaires for data collection. The results indicate that most students in the Language and Literature programme are aware of the pluri-centrality of the Portuguese language but are unaware of the specific relationship between the language and East Timor.

Still within the field of reflections on curricular issues, the fifth paper is entitled **Analysis of entry, permanence, and dropout of students in the Spanish language course at UFPB – Distance Learning modality**, by Emanuel de Abreu Silva and José Veranildo Lopes da Costa Junior from the Federal University of Paraíba (UFPB). It reflects on the teaching of Spanish in Brazil for over more than a hundred years, highlighting moments of institutionalisation and attempts of obstructions due to different language policies. The study is grounded in Applied Linguistics and analyses quantitative data on enrollment, dropout, and graduates from the Language and Literature (Spanish) programme (DL modality), at the Federal University of Paraíba from 2017 to 2022.

Continuing in the same perspective, the sixth paper, titled **Reconceptualization of the Libras discipline at a Federal University in Mato Grosso do Sul: a portrait before and after Decree 5,626/05**, is presented by Jakellinny Gonçalves de Souza Rizzo and Josiane Peres Gonçalves from the Federal University of Mato Grosso do Sul (UFMS). It aims to analyse the history of the Libras (Brazilian Sign Language) discipline in the Pedagogy course at UFMS (Pantanal Campus – CPAN), covering the period before and after the Decree No. 5,626/2005, which made it mandatory in teacher training courses. The research analysed some Programme Pedagogical Projects (PPC, in Portuguese) from 2000 to 2020, in order to understand how the Libras discipline was incorporated into the programmes. The study observed that the Libras discipline has little visibility in the curriculum, highlighting the need for reorganisation to train teachers capable of meeting the specific needs of deaf students in Elementary Education.

Moving onto the field of media genres, the seventh paper is titled **The sociodiscursive image of professor Noslen Borges in a post on Instagram**, by Fabiana Almeida Aparecida de Pinto and Thiago Madureira de Alvarenga from the Federal Center of Technological Education of Minas Gerais (CEFET-MG). The authors discuss the socio-discursive image of the teacher Noslen Borges, using the metafunctions of Visual Design Grammar as an analytical tool. The research starts from the perception that, in order to reach young people on social media, teachers need to adjust their ethos, i.e. the socio-discursive image, to contribute to the mass dissemination of knowledge on Instagram. The paper aims to analyse the ethos projected by the teacher in his Instagram posts and to understand how it contributes to the dissemination of knowledge in the Portuguese language. The study highlights that the teacher uses semiotic elements to build a persuasive discourse on social media, projecting a fun, playful, and relaxed ethos to attract as many followers as possible.

Following that, the eighth paper presented is **The didacticization of labor writing in the teacher training course: didactic sequence, learning through reviews**, by Renilson Nóbrega Gomes and Williany Miranda da Silva from the Federal University of Campina Grande (UFCG). It addresses the relationship between mastering a genre and its application in discourse projects in the school context. The study focuses on teacher training based on the didactic treatment of the labour genre in the didactic sequence. The aims include identifying didactisation processes of this genre in the course "Didactic Sequence: learning through reviews", besides analysing the perspectives of teacher training that emerge from this process. The results indicate that the didactisation of the didactic sequence focuses more on the teaching and production of reviews than on the specific treatment of the labour genre.

The ninth paper is titled **The media convergence in Wandavision: revisionism and contamination of the genre**, by Andre Aparecido de Medeiros and Jéssica da Silva Nascimento from the State University of Paraíba (UEPB). The authors propose an analysis of media convergence in the series WandaVision (2021), exploring its media transformations and revisionist approach in the context of the Marvel cinematic universe. The paper considers WandaVision as an example of "contamination", as proposed by Baetens, indicating an innovation in the format. The analysis focuses on specific scenes of the series, such as commercials and the addition of elements to the medium, suggesting the existence of "another story". The concept of contamination

is discussed in relation to storytelling structures, highlighting how the series uses these structures to tell an additional narrative throughout its plot.

Delving into the literary field, the tenth paper, **Márcia Kambeba's poetry and its reception in the school context**, is presented by Catharie Brandão de Souza and José Hélder Pinheiro from the Federal University of Campina Grande (UFCG). It addresses the lack of knowledge about indigenous peoples in classrooms, emphasising that this gap perpetuates prejudices, lack of respect, and a scarcity of recognition of ancestral cultures. The main aim is to reflect on the work of the indigenous poet Márcia Kambeba and to share an experience involving some of her poems in the school context.

Afterwards, the eleventh paper is **Echoes of Ophelia: A Comparative Analysis of the Character in the Poetry of Arthur Rimbaud and Anne Perrier**, by Paola Karyne Azevedo Jochimsen from the University of Coimbra. The author proposes a comparative analysis of the representation of the character Ophelia in William Shakespeare's play "Hamlet" (1599), highlighting her centrality in the arts and poetry throughout the centuries. The focus of the analysis is on two French-language works: "Ophélie" (1870) by Arthur Rimbaud, and "Le Livre d'Ophélie" (1979) by Anne Perrier. The theoretical approach is anchored in Bachelard's reflections on the character and Wölfflin's aesthetic considerations. The analysis explores how each poet portrays Ophelia, a character initially secondary in "Hamlet" that has generated enduring fascination in the arts and literature.

In the same literary domain, the twelfth paper, **Carnivalization in the Film Adaptation Alice in Wonderland by Tim Burton** is presented by Ismael Arruda Nazário da Silva and Charles Albuquerque Ponte from the State University of Rio Grande do Norte (UERN). It proposes an analysis of Tim Burton's 2010 film adaptation of "Alice in Wonderland", focusing on understanding Carnivalization, according to Bakhtinian concepts. Carnivalization refers to an event where the popular layer of society has the opportunity to participate in social processes traditionally reserved for a class holding power, resulting in role reversals and producing laughter or mockery. Using Bakhtin's works on Carnivalization and Discini's contribution, the study analyses five scenes from Tim Burton's film in order to understand how Carnivalization manifests in cinematic narrative.

Closing the section of papers, the thirteenth one is **Bom-Crioulo by Adolfo Caminha: peculiarities of a naturalistic representation of homoeroticism and its literary reception** by Cyro Nascimento from the Federal University of Rio Grande do Norte (UFRN). The author analyses

the reception of the naturalistic novel "Bom-Crioulo", by the Ceará-born writer Adolfo Caminha, exploring the various interpretations the work has received since its publication over a hundred years ago. The focus of the paper is to understand how the representation of homoeroticism in the narrative was crucial in generating public interest while simultaneously provoking repulsion from part of contemporary and subsequent critics.

This edition also features a translation of a literary excerpt from the memoir "The Latehomecomer: A Hmong Family Memoir" (2018), by Hmong-American author Kao Kalia Yang, titled ***Aquela que volta tarde***, translated by Priscila Campolina de Sá Campello and Tiago Ruas Dieguez from the Pontifical Catholic University of Minas Gerais (PUC Minas). Additionally, there are the following poems: ***Poema branco, poema tinto***, by José d'Assunção Barros from the Federal Rural University of Rio de Janeiro (UFRRJ), ***Obnubilado***, by Adson Luan Duarte Vilasboas Seba from the State University of Mato Grosso (UNEMAT), ***Solidão é um substantivo coletivo***, by Joilson Bessa da Silva from the Municipal Network of Campos dos Goytacazes (SMECE/PMCG) and Duque de Caxias (SMEDC/PMDC), and ***Poesias***, by Vanderley Aguiar from the State University of Ceará (UECE).

Dear reader, this third edition of 2023 presents papers that stimulate diverse reflections in the field of Language and Literature, including: *Dialogism of Language, Socio-discursive Interactionism, Discourse Analysis, Beliefs, Applied Linguistics, Didactics, Media Genres, Indigenous Literature, Comparative Literature, Literary Adaptation for Cinema, and Literary Reception*, ultimately exploring Languages in contemporaneity.

Thus, we conclude the year 2023, hoping that intolerance and geopolitical conflicts give way to dialogue, reflection, discussion, and scientific advancement, allowing us to live in more just, fulfilling, and peaceful societies.

That is our will. We wish you all a great reading!

PhD. Prof. [Alain-Philippe Durand](#), University of Arizona, USA

PhD. Prof. [Josilene Pinheiro-Mariz](#), Federal University of Campina Grande, Brazil

PhD. Prof. [Maria Rennally Soares da Silva](#), Federal University of Paraíba, Brazil

Organisers of the issue **Languages and Literatures in contemporaneity**

Revista Letras Raras

ISSN: 2317-2347 – n. 3, v. 12, (2023)

Todo o conteúdo da RLR está licenciado sob Creative Commons Atribuição 4.0 Internacional

Revista Letras Raras: Scholarly Journal of the LELLC Research Group / Laboratory of Studies in Linguistics, Literature, and Languages in Contemporaneity / Federal University of Campina Grande.

Translated by Rafael de Arruda Sobral